

The Role of Populism in Democratic Processes

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Abstract

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Populism, a multifaceted phenomenon in modern politics, may have a substantial influence on democratic processes. This essay seeks to analyze the impact of populism on democratic processes, including both its beneficial and detrimental effects. The impact of populism on the operation of representative democracy, political engagement, and political decision-making processes are significant subjects of discourse in the literature. This

essay seeks to provide a theoretical framework for comprehending the impact of populism on democracy. It will then examine the tactics used by populist leaders and the consequences of populist movements on democratic institutions.

Keywords: *Populism, Democracy, Populist Leaders, Democratic Institutions*

Introduction

Democracy and populism are often analyzed and researched in the fields of political science and social sciences. Both of them have significant roles in political processes, but they possess distinct traits and priorities. Democracy is a system of governance that establishes the foundation of people sovereignty and participatory politics. Essentially, the primary objective of democracy is to facilitate the active involvement of individuals in political procedures, allowing them to choose leaders who will act as their representatives and giving them the ability to influence governmental decisions. Democracy has several manifestations, however, often encompasses fundamental tenets such as electoral processes, unrestricted intellectual and verbal discourse, adherence to legal frameworks, and protection of human liberties and entitlements. Populism is a political tactic often used by political leaders to garner popular support. Populist leaders often rally the public by establishing simplified divisions, such as "us" against "them," and assert themselves as the authoritative representatives of the people.

Populist discourse often highlights the rejection of privileged individuals and established political establishments, asserting that the leader embodies the collective will of the populace. Nevertheless, there exist varying perspectives about the definition and attributes of populism, which may potentially result in both favorable outcomes such as heightened public engagement, as well as unfavorable repercussions like heightened polarization and the erosion of democratic institutions. While democracy and populism may coexist within the same political sphere, democracy tends to be characterized by stronger institutional structures and a longer-term perspective. Populism is a political approach characterized by a focus on short-

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term goals, emotional appeals, and a strong emphasis on the leader. Nevertheless, these factors play a crucial role in the realm of politics and, when examined in conjunction, they may enhance our comprehension of social and political processes.

The correlation between populism and democracy is a very intricate and captivating field within contemporary politics. The definition and use of some ideas in political science have sparked considerable controversy throughout the years (Gallie, 1956). Populism has gained significant prominence in the field of political science, particularly in the latter half of the 20th century. It has been extensively examined and debated in many settings.

Analyzing the impact of populism on democratic institutions and examining the possible threats to democracy are the focal points of contemporary political discourse. The essay explored the interplay between populism and democratic systems, considering several scholarly perspectives and analyzing the potential impact of this interaction on democracy.

Within this particular framework, Ernesto Let us begin by seeing populism as an indication of democracy, as defined by Laclau. Laclau argues that populist politics might facilitate the establishment of a radical democracy that acknowledges and prioritizes many identities and demands, while also promoting active citizen engagement (Laclau, 2007). This theory posits that populism reconfigures the inherent conflict between the populace and the governing authorities by creating a dichotomy within society: the ruling class and the marginalized, so promoting the process of democracy.

Chantal Mouffe's perspective is influenced by a comparable framework. Mouffe argues that left populist movements have the potential to establish new political structures in a context where egalitarian and democratic principles are being undermined (Mouffe, 2019). This approach highlights the possible impact of populism on the restructuring of democratic systems.

Nevertheless, there are perspectives that contend that populism might potentially jeopardize democracy. According to Benjamin Arditì and other experts, populism is a significant and concerning presence in democratic politics (Arditì, 2010). Arditì argues that populism, by

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deviating from the established norms of political conduct, poses a fundamental threat to the core values of liberal democracy.

The conflicting perspectives presented illustrate the intricate nature of the connection between populism and democracy. The objective of the paper is to consolidate diverse scholarly methods in comprehending the link between populism and democracy.

AIM

This essay aims to thoroughly analyze the function and impact of populism on democratic processes. The objective is to elucidate the precise definition and distinctive features of populism, while also offering a theoretical framework for comprehending the impact of populism on democracy. In addition, the essay analyzes the correlation between populist leaders and democratic norms, their influence on social involvement, their connection to democratic stability, and their effect on public support and election processes.

The essay tries to examine the reasons and limitations of populism in contributing to democracy by analyzing its challenges to democratic institutions and its role in democratic processes. Ultimately, the paper examines how populism affects the process of democratization and its positive contributions to democracy. Additionally, it provides recommendations for further study in this area. The paper seeks to comprehend the functions of populism in democratic procedures and formulate tactics to safeguard democracy.

RESULTS

Research on the link between populism and democracy uncovers many conclusions. Initially, an analysis was conducted on the impact of populism on democracy and its associated institutions. This environment highlights the autocratic inclinations of populist leaders, underscoring their lack of consistency with both popular backing and democratic principles.

According to Laclau's thesis, several experts believe that populism has the potential to enhance democratic institutions. According to their perspective, populist politics may play a role in

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establishing a transformative democracy that acknowledges and prioritizes many identities and demands, while also promoting active engagement of citizens (Laclau, 2007). Nevertheless, there are those who hold a contrary perspective. According to Arditì and other experts, populism has been identified as a potential danger to democracy. According to Arditì (2010), populism is seen by them as a threatening presence in democratic politics.

Another discovery indicates that populism has the potential to undermine democracy and undermine democratic principles. Specifically, when analyzing the methods used by populist leaders in democratic processes and their interactions with democratic institutions, possible threats to democracy become apparent. The analytical results elucidate the impact of populism on democratic processes. The results demonstrate the response of democratic institutions and procedures to the impact of populism, as well as the level of resilience of the basic ideals that underpin democracy against populism. The results about the resilience and flexibility of democracy against populism are significant in this particular setting (Dahl, 1971; Schmitter & Karl, 1991).

While the writers of the American constitution included significant measures to ensure the smooth operation of democratic processes, it is crucial to acknowledge their influence on the conduct of individuals during electoral processes. The fundamental tenet of Madison's strategy is to thwart the populace from generating unattainable requisitions inside a democratic framework. Nevertheless, according to EE Schattschneider, an effective democratic system should safeguard the people from making unrealistic demands (Brunello, 2018: 109). The study of the rise of national liberation movements and populism after the French Revolution demonstrates the impact of this era on democratic procedures (Wiebe, 2002).

In order to comprehend the impact of populism on democratic processes, it is crucial to focus on the notion of "the people" as defined by Abraham Lincoln in his conception of democracy. Nevertheless, political machinations may sometimes weaken this idea, causing it to serve the interests of certain political elites rather than the genuine desire of the people (Bond & Smith, 2013).

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Populist leaders often garner support by appealing to large crowds. Nevertheless, this assistance often functions to bolster the personal or partisan agendas of leaders rather than being based on the genuine requirements of the populace. Hence, populism may have intricate influences on democratic processes.

When evaluating the impact of populism on democratic processes, it is crucial to consider the use of the notion of the people and the true motives of populist leaders. Nevertheless, to safeguard democratic principles and establishments, it is essential to acknowledge the dangers associated with populism and sustain a state of equilibrium.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The historical progression of democracy, the many forms of democracy that arose in the United Kingdom and the United States, and the subsequent evolution of these models have had a substantial influence on the operation of democratic processes and institutions (Yentür, 2024). The United Kingdom saw the establishment of representative democracy throughout the 17th century when the middle class used its economic influence to enhance the authority of Parliament. Similarly, the establishment of the United States of America in the 18th century served as a significant illustration of representative democracy, characterized by its presidential administration. These dynamics facilitated the expansion of democracy and the development of many types of democracy (Huntington, 1991).

In order to comprehend the impact of populism on democratic procedures, it is crucial to get a comprehensive understanding of the definition and mechanics of populism. Ernesto Laclau and Chantal Mouffe, theorists in the field, describe populism as a political discourse that revolves on the opposition between "us" and "them" (Laclau, 2005). Populist leaders often assert their representation of the so-called "silent majority" in society and stress their opposition to the "elites." The use of confrontational language has the potential to elicit strong emotional reactions from society and enhance political engagement. However, it may also contribute to the division of society and undermine the strength of democratic institutions.

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Populism is grounded on the theoretical framework of popular democracy and direct public engagement (Bond and Smith, 2013). These understandings seek to foster a more intimate connection with political processes by highlighting the active involvement and impact of the general population.

The democratic procedures seen in Swiss cantons and small communities in the USA have common characteristics with populism. Through the use of referendums and initiatives, the general public has the ability to actively participate in decision-making processes and exert influence on policy formation. This aligns with the principles of "popular sovereignty" and "direct democracy" advocated by populist politicians.

Latin America has a range of experiences with popular democracy and direct public engagement, for instance. Evo Morales in Bolivia the Morales-led administration has undertaken a range of populist initiatives aimed at enhancing the involvement and representation of indigenous populations. These policies include referendums that promote direct democracy, laws that guarantee the active involvement of local people in development initiatives, and policies that prioritize indigenous culture and values.

In addition, Iceland's democratic procedures during the 2008 fiscal crisis serve as a significant illustration of popular democracy and direct public involvement. In response to the political and economic challenges that arose after the crisis, the people of Iceland have implemented many approaches to participatory democracy and actively promoted direct public involvement in order to seek answers. An online platform called "Icelandic Constitution" was established to facilitate public engagement in the process of constitutional revision and gather public input and recommendations.

In recent years, Poland has seen many practices and projects aimed at promoting direct public engagement at the local level. For instance, in Poland, local administrations hold community meetings and participatory budgeting procedures as components of popular democracy. Neighborhood meetings serve as a forum for residents to express their thoughts about local concerns, engage in discussions about problems, and suggest potential solutions. Participatory

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budgeting allows residents to actively engage in the process of deciding and allocating the local budget, therefore emphasizing the importance of people's preferences and requirements.

Türkiye showcases several instances of widespread democracy and direct engagement of the people. In recent years, the government has implemented a range of programs and practices with the goal of enhancing public involvement in local governance and public policy, which have garnered significant attention.

For instance, the local assemblies and participatory budget processes implemented by municipalities in Türkiye exemplify popular democracy. Neighborhood councils serve as forums for residents to engage in discussions on matters concerning their communities, actively contribute to the decision-making process, and provide remedies for local difficulties. Participatory budgeting allows residents to directly participate in the decision-making and allocation of the local budget. These methods enhance the transparency and inclusivity of decision-making processes in local governments, promoting increased openness and involvement in democratic procedures.

Furthermore, Türkiye showcases popular democracy via the implementation of several campaigns and protest movements orchestrated by non-governmental organizations and activist groups. For instance, demonstrations orchestrated by environmental activists to oppose projects that inflict damage upon the natural environment and gatherings arranged by advocates for women's rights to denounce violence against women provide an opportunity for the general people to express their opinions and actively engage in political proceedings.

These examples demonstrate the significance of popular democracy and direct public engagement in comprehending the role of populism in democratic processes. These strategies may enhance the robustness of democratic institutions and uphold democratic principles, while promoting more public engagement in political processes.

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Nevertheless, the influence of populism on democratic institutions is intricate and cannot be solely attributed to direct public involvement. Populism often employs a leader-centric strategy, stressing the assertion that the leader embodies the interests of the people, rather than promoting direct involvement of the people. It is evident in this scenario that populist politicians have a tendency to undermine democratic institutions instead of enhancing them.

It is crucial to assess the influence of populism on democratic institutions in this particular situation. Further investigation is required to examine the impact of popular democracy and direct public engagement on the outcomes of populism, as well as the influence on democratic institutions. This has the potential to be a significant milestone in ensuring the smooth operation of democratic processes and safeguarding democratic principles.

The involvement of individuals in democratic procedures and the influence of populism are intricately connected to the historical development of democracy and the formation of various democratic models. Throughout history, the role of the people has undergone significant transformations, from ancient Greece to the evolution of contemporary democracy to the present day. In ancient Greece, democratic procedures included the participation of males in public assemblies, and the administration was exclusively carried out by men (Sabine, 1969: 4). The theoretical underpinnings of populism are influenced by the idea that the desires and preferences of the general population are of utmost importance. Populism suggests a kind of governance where the connection between the people and the leader is formed directly.

Throughout history, national liberation struggles, and the emergence of populism have underscored the significance of the popular will and the dynamic between leaders and the people. To comprehend the beginnings of these movements, it is necessary to examine fundamental ideological frameworks, such as JJ Rousseau's notion of the "volonté general". In populism, the people's connection with the leader is formed naturally and does not rely on any kind of representation or institutional framework. This strategy highlights the straightforwardness of the connection between the leader and the people, portraying the people as morally upright and the elites as wicked and unethical.

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During the decades after the French Revolution, the emergence of national liberation groups facilitated the ascent of populism. For instance, the Narodnichestvo movement in Russia and the People's Movement in the USA. The Party advocated for the interests and needs of the peasant class and small farmers (Kalaycıoğlu, 2019).

Liberal democracy is a political system that promotes active political engagement, allows for unrestricted expression of diverse views, and gives the populace a role in governance. This system adheres to the notion of the rule of law, ensuring that all individuals are subject to the same legal standards and possess equal rights under the law. Furthermore, the promotion of plurality and variety takes precedence, facilitating the peaceful discussion and resolution of divergent perspectives.

Nevertheless, populism has the potential to endanger the principles and functioning of liberal democracy. Populist leaders often prioritize the viewpoints of their own followers and may attempt to stifle opposing views. This scenario has the potential to result in the erosion of pluralism and the curtailment of freedom of speech. Moreover, the autocratic inclinations of populist leaders have the potential to undermine the supremacy of legal principles and undermine the strength of democratic establishments.

Hence, it is crucial to conserve and enhance the core tenets of liberal democracy. For democracy to work effectively, it is crucial to uphold the principles of the rule of law, freedom of speech, and plurality. Furthermore, it is essential to enhance public consciousness about the perils of populism and bolster dedication to democratic principles. By adopting this approach, liberal democracy may effectively withstand the impact of populism and guarantee the uninterrupted progression of democratic procedures.

An instance of liberal democracy in Türkiye may be seen via the implementation of a multi-party-political framework and the conduction of transparent and equitable elections. Türkiye implemented a multi-party system in 1946, which led to the frequent occurrence of general elections. Multiple political parties have the liberty to propose candidates in elections, and voters have the autonomy to freely exercise their choices. The circumstance exemplifies the

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promotion of political engagement in Türkiye, allowing for the unrestricted expression of many political perspectives (Yentür, 2024).

Liberal democracy and populist democracy are distinct in terms of their architecture and operations within democratic regimes. Liberal democracy is a political system that upholds pluralism and the rule of law, ensuring the safeguarding of people's basic rights and freedoms. It is founded on the tenets of representative democracy and typically functions on the basis of the separation of powers among the legislative, executive, and judicial departments. Liberal democracies are characterized by government powers that are constrained by constitutional constraints, and they have an autonomous judicial system that safeguards the rights of citizens.

Populist democracy, in contrast, is a political system where leaders acquire power or are chosen directly by the people, in accordance with the popular desire. Populist leaders sometimes amass support by creating divisions throughout society via the use of simple notions like "us" against "them" and by capitalizing on the public's emotional responses. Populist democracy typically downplays the significance of the concept of separation of powers and other fundamental foundations of liberal democracy. Instead, it highlights the leader's predominant power in decision-making processes.

To comprehend the role of populism in democratic processes, it is crucial to distinguish between liberal democracy and populist democracy in this particular setting. Liberal democracy is characterized by a structural architecture that restricts government authority and safeguards individual liberties. In contrast, populist democracy tends to adopt a more centralized and authoritarian approach. An analysis of the influence of populism on democratic processes should consider the distinctions between these two frameworks.

ANALYSIS OF POPULIST STRATEGIES

The notion of populist strategy is crucial for comprehending the impact of populism on the political realm. Populist leaders often use tactics such as using simpler communications, appealing to emotions, and making decisions based on their personal authority. The primary

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objective of these techniques is to attract substantial audiences, enhance political engagement, and acquire popular endorsement. Populist leaders often prioritize the needs and desires of the lowest socioeconomic groups. Nevertheless, these tactics may also engender impractical anticipations, foster a dearth of profundity in political discourse, and undermine democratic institutions. Hence, it is crucial to examine populist tactics in order to comprehend their influence on democratic procedures and safeguard democratic establishments.

Populism often employs fundamental methods that revolve on a political language centered on the opposition between "us" and "them" (Laclau, 2005). The use of confrontational language has the potential to elicit strong emotional reactions from society and enhance political engagement. However, it may also contribute to the division of society and undermine the strength of democratic institutions.

Populist leaders often assert their representation of the so-called "silent majority" in society and stress their opposition to the "elites." This battle is a key tactic of populism and highlights the stark gap between the general population and the privileged ruling class. This juxtaposition generates a milieu characterized by perpetual discord and fortifies the dynamic between the leader and the people.

Another fundamental strategy of populism is to categorize individuals into absolute divisions, such as black-white or good-evil. The general populace is portrayed as idealized, characterized by purity, cleanliness, and virtue, but the ruling class is seen as malevolent, colonialistic, and lacking in moral principles. Although this classification might enhance the sense of cohesion and camaraderie within a community, it can also intensify division and polarization.

In order to comprehend the impact of populism on democratic processes, it is crucial to analyze the functioning and implementation of these fundamental techniques. Studying the influence of populist leaders' rhetoric on society and its effects on democratic institutions might enhance our comprehension of this matter (Laclau, 2005; Mudde, 2004).

Within this particular framework, it is crucial to examine the ramifications of populist tactics on the functioning of democratic systems. The influence of populism on democracy is often complex and encompasses several aspects. Populist leaders' policies have the potential to

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impact the operation of democratic institutions and the level of political engagement within society.

Examining the influence of populist tactics on democratic procedures is crucial for the vitality of democratic establishments and the engagement of people in political affairs. This research is a crucial instrument for comprehending the influence of populism on democracy and may aid in formulating efficient policy approaches to enhance democratic institutions.

Populist leaders often use simple communications and emotive implications to elicit emotional reactions from the audience, hence enhancing political engagement. Nevertheless, these tactics may also engender impractical anticipations and lead to a dearth of profundity in political discussions. This position poses a potential risk to the effective operation of democratic processes.

The influence of populist leaders on democratic institutions is also remarkable. Populist leaders may sometimes weaken democratic institutions and exhibit authoritarian inclinations. Populist leaders often exert pressure on democratic institutions by relying on their personal power to make decisions. This condition might potentially jeopardize the robust operation of democratic processes.

Studying the effects of populist techniques on democratic processes is crucial for understanding how democratic institutions operate, political engagement, and society's dedication to democratic principles. This research may aid in identifying efficacious policy approaches to enhance democratic institutions and ensure the long-term viability of democracy.

THE EFFECT OF POPULISM ON DEMOCRATIC INSTITUTIONS

Populist movements may enhance democratic involvement. Populist leaders often articulate the immediate needs of the populace and enhance engagement in political procedures. This has the potential to reach a wide range of people and promote engagement in political activities. Weyland (2001) contends that populist movements have the ability to draw more societal focus

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towards political processes. Mudde and Kaltwasser (2017) highlight the capacity of populist leaders' tactics to influence the public and garner support by appealing to broad audiences.

Another advantageous characteristic of populism is its ability to articulate discontent with existing political structures and ruling classes. This has the potential to provide an opportunity for system improvement. Populist leaders often attract support from the lowest echelons of society and prioritize their demands and grievances in the political discourse. This has the potential to stimulate the political determination required to address longstanding neglected issues.

Nevertheless, the impact of populism on democratic institutions also presents significant hazards. Populist politicians with authoritarian inclinations pose a threat to democratic norms and institutions. The study conducted by Mudde and Rovira Kaltwasser (2017) demonstrates that populism has the potential to undermine democratic institutions and diminish confidence across different institutions. Populist politicians often seek to weaken democratic checks and balances. This has the potential to undermine the autonomy of the legislative and judicial branches and result in the concentration of executive authority.

A phenomena that has both potential benefits and potential hazards. Populist movements have the capacity to enhance democratic engagement and provide a chance to revamp the political system. Nevertheless, the autocratic inclinations of populist leaders and their interference in democratic institutions might jeopardize the robust operation of democracy. Further investigation is required to comprehend the impact of populism on democratic procedures, and appropriate actions must be implemented to safeguard democratic principles. Safeguarding the autonomy and efficacy of democratic establishments is a primary strategy to protect democracy from the authoritarian inclinations of populism (Levitsky & Ziblatt, 2018; Sadurski, 2019; Esen & Gümüşçü, 2017; Mudde & Rovira Kaltwasser, 2017).

However, the influence of populism on democratic institutions is intricately linked to the operational and structural aspects of democracy. An analysis should be conducted to explore how the institutional structures required for the smooth operation of democratic processes

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influence the impact of populism. Within this particular framework, it is crucial to direct attention towards the clash and interplay between populism and the fundamental tenets of democracy (Schmitter & Karl, 1991). The influence of populism on democratic institutions is intricately linked to the operation and institutional structures of democratic processes. The resilience and flexibility of democratic institutions in response to the impact of populism are crucial for the longevity of democracy. An examination of the influence of populism on democratic institutions assesses the strength of democratic principles in the presence of populism and its potential consequences for the future of democracy (Brunello, 2018; Sabine, 1969).

The impact of populism on democratic processes is complex and encompasses both advantageous and detrimental consequences. While populist leaders may enhance political engagement, it is important to acknowledge that they may also undermine democratic institutions. Hence, more investigation is necessary to comprehend the impact of populism on democratic procedures, and steps should be implemented to fortify and safeguard democratic institutions. Analyzing the influence of populism on democratic institutions is crucial for the sustainable progression of the democratization process (Schmitter & Karl, 1991). To comprehend the impact of populism on democratic processes, it is necessary to undertake multidisciplinary studies and conduct long-term study (Yentür, 2024).

CONCLUSION

The impact of populism on democratic processes is an intricate and multifaceted phenomena. Populist groups and leaders have the capacity to enhance democratic participation, generate public interest in political processes, and articulate discontent with existing political systems, so making valuable contributions to the operation of democracy. Nevertheless, alongside these favorable outcomes, it is crucial to acknowledge the autocratic inclinations of populism, as well as the potential threat it poses to democratic principles and the erosion of confidence amongst institutions. The actions of populist leaders, who concentrate executive authority and

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undermine oversight systems, pose significant risks to the long-term viability of democratic institutions.

When assessing the impact of populism on democratic processes, it becomes evident that populist groups and leaders provide both advantages and disadvantages. Populism has the potential to foster engagement in democratic processes and facilitate the transformation of the political system by directly incorporating the demands of the people into the political agenda.

Nevertheless, the authoritarian inclinations of populism and its capacity to erode democratic standards are at odds with the core tenets of liberal democracy. Specifically, the inclination of populist leaders to consolidate executive authority and undermine oversight systems might endanger the autonomy of legislative and judicial institutions.

Suggestions

Enhancing Democratic Institutions: It is essential to reinforce check and balance mechanisms in order to safeguard the autonomy and effectiveness of democratic institutions. It is crucial to safeguard the autonomy of the legislative, executive, and judicial branches, and to guarantee opposition to the autocratic inclinations of populist leaders.

Guaranteeing the Rule of Law: Safeguarding and enforcing the rule of law is crucial for the smooth operation of democratic procedures. The preservation of judicial independence is vital in the face of populist politicians' efforts to meddle with the court.

Enhancing Civil Society: Non-governmental groups and independent media outlets should be reinforced as components of democratic oversight processes. These groups may enhance the operation of democratic processes by augmenting public access to information and the openness of government policy.

Education and awareness raising initiatives are necessary to enhance public understanding and knowledge of democratic principles and procedures. This may promote the commitment to democratic principles without yielding to the allure of populist rhetoric.

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Enhancing collaboration among international institutions and democratic nations may effectively counteract the authoritarian inclinations of populist leaders, therefore fostering global opposition. Ensuring the safeguarding of democratic values and human rights is a crucial measure.

Further investigation is required to comprehend the impact of populism on democratic procedures. Specifically, the integration of several academic disciplines and conducting research over an extended period of time would enhance our comprehension of the enduring impacts of populism on democratic institutions.

RESTRICTION

The research is limited to scientific research that has been previously conducted and published in the literature.

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ETHICAL STATEMENT

Publication ethics of journal; scientific research and publications are based on fundamental principles such as honesty, openness, objectivity, and respect for the findings and creations of others.

aims to ensure that it is carried out in accordance with the principles and for this to happen, It is a national-based scientific organization that aims to achieve these principles in the field of social sciences.

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RESOURCE

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